

Checklist of the Bird Species from the Ruzizi Delta, Northern End of Lake Tanganyika, in Burundi and the Democratic Republic of Congo

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ABSTRACT

The checklist of bird species from the Ruzizi Delta in Burundi and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) was investigated from April 2019 until August 2021 at five sites in the Rusizi Burundian Delta and five sites in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta. Each site was visited three times a year during the years 2019, 2020 and 2021. The investigation was conducted by direct observation on transect counts, point counts and on road bird counting, using binoculars and a telescope. Travel was facilitated by the motorized fiberglass boat and the double cabin field vehicle of the Centre for Research in Hydrobiology (CRH) in Uvira, DRC. The Ruzizi Delta includes terrestrial dry areas in wooded and tree-steppe, marshes, rivers, ponds and the northern shoreline of Lake Tanganyika in Bujumbura (Burundi) and Uvira (DRC). On the coast and on the ponds, the investigation sometimes resorted to traveling in non-motorized canoes to inform us, among other things, of illegal exploitation in supposedly protected areas. At the end of our investigations, we have drawn up the list of 18 orders, 84 families and 490 species of birds that we present in this publication.

Key words - Checklist of bird species; Order of bird species; Family of bird species; Bird point counts; Transect counts of birds.

INTRODUCTION

The checklist of bird species of the Ruzizi Delta (RD) in Burundi and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) was investigated from April 2019 until August 2021 in five sites of the Rusizi Burundian (RBD) Delta and five sites of the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD). Each site was visited three times a year during the years 2019, 2020 and 2021. Following documents are published about birds for the Ruzizi Delta in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) and in the Republic of Burundi. Ornithological importance of DRC and conservation issues in protected and unprotected areas including wetland areas, are published by (Demey & Louette, 2001). The Rusizi Burundian Delta is an Important Bird Areas (Nkezabahizi & Manirambona, 2011), (Dowset & Dowset-Lemaire, 1993) and (Gaugris, 1979).

Authors (Ntakimazi, Nzigidahera, Nicayenzi, & West, 2000) inventoried 120 bird species and their terrestrial or aquatic biotopes in the Rusizi Burundian Delta. Finally the

following authors (Nkezabahizi & Bizimana, 2008) investigated Burundi's Important Bird Areas Status and Trends 2008 listing only two birds, the White-winged Tern (*Chlidonia leucopterus*) and the African Skimmer (*Rynchops flavirostris*) fulfilling the Ramsar Criteria A4i and A1 in the Rusizi Natural Reserve. The very rich ornithological fauna of Rusizi Burundian National Park and Ramsar site includes 350 sedentary and migratory bird species (MEEATU, Ramsar, & WWF, 2014).

How to Cite this Article:

Bashing Bishobibiri Alexis, Eric Sande, Charles Kahindo & Gaspard Ntakimazi. (2023). Checklist of the Bird Species from the Ruzizi Delta, Northern End of Lake Tanganyika, in Burundi and the Democratic Republic of Congo. *Biolife*, 11(2), 115-129.

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8010927>

Received: 18 April 2023; Accepted: 30 May 2023;

Published online: 6 June, 2023.

For his dissertation, the graduate student Apollinaire Ntakiyica (Ntakiyica, 2008) investigated the State of knowledge on the distribution sites of ornithological fauna in Burundi. He presented 638 bird species for Burundi of which 410 were listed in the Rusizi Burundian Delta.

My doctoral research is unique to investigate bird checklist simultaneously in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD) in DRC and the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD) in Burundi. It has updated the list of bird species in the RCD and the RBD. It will contribute to the Ruzizi Congolese Wetland Protection for bird and biodiversity conservation, strengthening the management of protected areas in Burundi with a view to combating climate change, epidemics and disasters and preventing the extinction of certain species of birds (Chapman A. D., 2009); (Butchart, Stattersfield, & Collar, 2006); (Chapman A. D., 2005); (Deanna, Brunner, Nige, Karr, & Nielsen, 1998). To constitute the bird checklist of Ruzizi Delta we referred essentially to the following authors (1) (Stevenson & Fanshawe, 2002); (2) (Fishpool & Evans, 2002); (3) (Williams & Arlott, 1988).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Areas Characteristics:

Study Area and Studied Sites

The Ruzizi delta extends from Vugizo, the point of separation of the small Ruzizi River from the Great Rusizi River with the Vugizo 1 site (Vug 1), S 03° 16' 08.5" E 029° 14' 27.1" 781 m altitude in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD) and Vugizo 2 (Vug 2), S 03° 16' 04" E 029° 14' 37" 779 m altitude in the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD) along the Grande Rusizi River to the Great Rusizi River Bridge (GRRB), S 03° 20' 33" E 029° 16' 25" 777 m altitude up to the Great Rusizi River Mouth (GRRM), S 03° 20' 27.8" E 029° 16' 23.5" 779 m above sea level, then along the shore of Lake Tanganyika towards the west passing through the Small Ruzizi River Mouth (SRRM), S 03° 21' 259" E 029° 12' 746" in the DRC, up to Kilomoni 2 (Kilo 2) Fishing Beach, S 03° 20' 49.2" E 029° 11' 30.7" then, turning north to the Nyangara pond (NyaP), S 03° 20' 22.4" E 029° 11' 42.9" 772 m above sea level, along the Small Ruzizi River towards the northeast as far as Vugizo, junction with the Grande Rusizi River (Figure 1).

Research Materials

A meter, a three meters length surveyor and a tape decametre were used to measure length, width, and depth of ponds, rivers, river banks and marshes;

A GPS was used to record geographical coordinates, length of sampling areas and sites;

A digital camera was used to capture birds and site features;

Three binoculars and a telescope were used in direct observation technique to distinguish birds; A vehicle and a medium ship were used for displacements;

We used bibliography from three institutional libraries including the CRH (Centre for Research in Hydrobiology) at Uvira, DRC; the CRSNE (Centre for Natural Research and Environment) of Burundi University, and the library of the Department of Zoology, Entomology and Fisheries Sciences of Makerere University, Kampala Uganda. Finally we checked Internet literature.

Research Methods

Regular weekly bird direct observations (Richer, 2018) were made in ten sites of two study areas, the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD) and the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD) from April 2019 to August 2021 for the period of 32 months to record all bird species seen and heard in the Ruzizi Delta. Birds were observed by direct observation (Richer, 2018) on transect counts, point counts and on road bird counting using binoculars and a telescope. They were identified using available field guides books: (Stevenson & Fanshawe, 2002); (Zimmerman, Turner, & Pearson, 1999); (Guggisberg, 1986); (Guggisberg, 1988) and (Williams & Arlott, 1988).

A) On transect counts

Birds were counted by transect counts using binoculars and a telescope in terrestrial areas for bird abundance and density calculations. With respect to the research questions and hypotheses, total number of birds seen was recorded as bird abundance and the total number of different bird species observed was recorded as species richness (Yee, 2022). That was because we are seeking to identify structural attributes that affect species richness and abundance in the Ruzizi Delta. Bird species identification was done using available above cited field guides. To draw the bird checklist we referred to (1) (Stevenson & Fanshawe, 2002); (2) (Fishpool & Evans, 2001); (3) (Williams & Arlott, 1988).

B) From point counts

Birds were sampled on point counts in marshes, ponds, bowls, in rivers and flood areas, for abundance and density calculations (Yee, 2022).

C) Bird Road Counting (BRC)

Birds were counted along roads from Kavimvira Customs Station (KCS) to Kavimvira Migration Post Offices (KMPO) in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD) and from Gatumba to Gatumba Migration Post Offices (GMPO) in the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD) (Yee, 2022).

GPS

GPS coordinates were recorded for study areas and studied sites habitats mapping.

Figure-1. Map showing the study areas and studied sites in Ruzizi Delta

Source: Our fieldwork of 2019-2021

RESULTS

Table-1 presents the checklist of 490 bird species distributed in 18 orders and 84 families. 301 (34%) species were recorded in the Ruzizi Congolese Delta (RCD) unprotected area; 387 (44%) species were recorded in the Rusizi Burundian Delta (RBD), 85% protected area; and 197 species were recorded both in the RCD and the RBD.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge Professor Louette Michel stuffed from the Royal Museum of Central Africa (RMCA) to have trained us for birds of Ruzizi Plain taxonomy during October, November and December 2008; Prof Dr. John Bates Curator of the Field Museum of Natural History Chicago USA, to have trained us in bird inventory techniques for the Kahuzi-Biega National Park, Muger forest and Idjwi Island using the P-BEATRA (Programme of Biodiversity of Ecosystems of Aquatic and Terrestrial of the Albertine Rift), 2001-2005; and all the members of my thesis Committee including Professors Eric Sande Corresponding author of this paper, Majaliwa Mwanjololo, both of them from the Makerere University Kampala Uganda, Charles Kahindo from the State University of Bukavu (UOB); Gaspard Ntakimazi and

Claver Sibomana from the University of Burundi, for their useful comments. We are thankful for the staff of CRH (Centre for Research in Hydrobiology at Uvira DRC, Doctoral School, University of Burundi and Makerere University Kampala Uganda for their devoutness every time when we needed their help. Finally we are thankful to anyone who directly or indirectly contributed to the production of this scientific publication.

Conflicts of Interest

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

Table-1. Checklist of the Bird Species from the Ruzizi Delta in Burundi and the Democratic Republic of Congo (RCD, Ruzizi Congolese Delta; RBD, Rusizi Burundian Delta; Nb, Number; Refer., References; 1 in RCD & RBD columns, present)

Order/ Family	Species Name	English Name	RCD	RBD	RCD RBD	Nb Refer.
Podicipediformes						
Podicipodidae	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	Little Grebe	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Podiceps cristatus</i>	Great Crested Grebe		1		1, 2
	<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	Black-necked Grebe	1	1		1, 2
Pelecaniformes						
Pelecanidae	<i>Pelecanus onocrotalus</i>	Great White Pelican	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Pelecanus rufescens</i>	Pink-backed Pelican	1	1	1	1, 2
Phalacrocoracidae	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	White-breasted Cormorant	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Phalacrocorax africanus</i>	Long-tailed Cormorant	1	1	1	1, 2
Anhingidae	<i>Anhinga rufa</i>	Darter	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Podica senegalensis</i>	African Finfoot	1	1	1	1, 2
Ciconiiformes						
Ardeidae	<i>Ixobrychus minutus</i>	Little Bittern	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ixobrychus stumii</i>	Dwarf Bittern	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	Black-crowned Night Heron	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle Egret	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ardeola ralloides</i>	Common Squacco Heron	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ardeola idea</i>	Madagascar Pond-heron		1		1, 2
	<i>Butorides striatus</i>	Green-backed Heron	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ardeola rufiventris</i>	Rufous-bellied Heron	1			1, 2
	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	Little Egret	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Egretta ardesiaca</i>	Black Heron	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Mesophoyx intermedia</i>	Intermediate Egret	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Casmerodius albus</i>	Great Egret	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ardea goliath</i>	Goliath Heron	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ardea purpurea</i>	Purple Heron	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Grey Heron	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ardea melanocephala</i>	Black-headed Heron	1	1	1	1, 2
Scopidae	<i>Scopus umbretta</i>	Hamerkop	1	1	1	1, 2
Ciconiidae	<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>	White Stork	1			1, 2
	<i>Mycteria ibis</i>	Yellow-billed Stork	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ciconia abdimii</i>	Abdim's Stork		1		1, 2
	<i>Ciconia episcopus</i>	White Stork	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Anastomus lamelligerinus</i>	African Open-billed Stork	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ephippiorhynchus senegalensis</i>	Saddle-billed Stork	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Leptoptilos crumeniferus</i>	Marabou Stork	1	1	1	1, 2
Threskiornithidae	<i>Threskiomis aethiopicus</i>	Sacred Ibis	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Bostrychia hagedash</i>	Hadada Ibis	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Plegadis falcinellus</i>	Glossy Ibis	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Bostrychia rara</i>	Spot-breasted Ibis	1			1, 2
Phoenicopteriformes						
Phoenicopteridae	<i>Platalea alba</i>	African Spoonbill	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Phoenicopterus ruber</i>	Greater Flamingo		1		1, 2
	<i>Phoenicopterus minor</i>	Lesser Flamingo		1		1, 2

Order/ Family	Species Name	English Name	RCD	RBD	RCD	Nb
					RBD	Refer.
	<i>Alopochen aegyptiacus</i>	Egyptian Goose	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Plectropterus gambensis</i>	Spur-winged Goose	1	1	1	1, 2
Anseriformes						
Anatidae	<i>Sarkidiornis melanotos</i>	Knob-billed Duck	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Nettapus auritus</i>	Pygmy Goose	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Dendrocygna viduata</i>	White-faced Whistling-Duck	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Dendrocygna bicolor</i>	Fulvous Whistling-Duck	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Pteronetta hartlaubii</i>	Hartlaub's Duck	1			1, 2
	<i>Anas erythroryncha</i>	Red-billed Teal	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Anas hottentota</i>	Hottentot Teal	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Anas capensis</i>	Cape Teal		1		1, 2
	<i>Thalassornis leuconotus</i>	White-backed Duck	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Anas undulata</i>	Yellow-billed Duck	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Anas sparsa</i>	African Black Duck		1		1, 2
	<i>Anas clypeata</i>	Northern Shoveler		1		1, 2
	<i>Anas acuta</i>	Pintail		1		1, 2
	<i>Anas querquedula</i>	Garganey	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Anas crecca</i>	Teal		1		1, 2
	<i>Anas penelope</i>	Wigeon		1		1, 2
	<i>Netta erythrophthalma</i>	Southern Pochard	1	1	1	1, 2
Falconiformes						
Accipitridae	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	Black Kite	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	Black-shouldered Kite	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Haliaeetus vocifer</i>	African Fish Eagle	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Gypohierax angolensis</i>	Palm-nut Vulture	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Pandion haliaetus</i>	Osprey	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Necrosyrtes monachus</i>	Hooded Vulture		1		1, 2
	<i>Trigonoceps occipitalis</i>	White-headed Vulture	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Torgos tracheliotus</i>	Lappet-faced Vulture		1		1, 2
	<i>Circus ranivorus</i>	African Marsh-Harrier	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Circus aeruginosus</i>	Eurasian Marsh-Harrier		1		1, 2
	<i>Circus pygargus</i>	Montagu's Harrier		1		1, 2
	<i>Circus macrourus</i>	Pallid Harrier		1		1, 2
	<i>Accipiter badius</i>	Shikra	1			1, 2
	<i>Accipiter ovampensis</i>	Ovambo sparrowhawk		1		1, 2
	<i>Accipiter minullus</i>	Little Sparrowhawk		1		1, 2
	<i>Polyboroides typus</i>	African Gymnogone	1			1, 2
	<i>Polyboroides radiatus</i>	Madagascar Gymnogone		1		1, 2
	<i>Buteo oreophilus</i>	Mountain (Forest) Buzzard		1		1, 2
	<i>Buteo rufofuscus</i>	Jackal Buzzard		1		1, 2
	<i>Aquila nipalensis</i>	Steppe Eagle		1		2, 3
	<i>Aquila wahlbergi</i>	Wahlberg's eagle		1		1, 2
	<i>Hieraetus spilogaster</i>	African Hawk Eagle		1		2, 3
	<i>Hieraetus pennatus</i>	Booted Eagle		1		2, 3
	<i>Aquila verreauxii</i>	Verreaux's Eagle		1		2, 3
	<i>Polemaetus bellicosus</i>	Martial Eagle		1		1, 2
	<i>Stephanoaetus coronatus</i>	African crowned eagle	1	1	1	1, 2
Falconidae	<i>Falco tinnunculus</i>	Common Kestrel	1	1	1	1, 2

Order/ Family	Species Name	English Name	RCD	RBD	RCD	Nb
					RBD	Refer.
	<i>Falco naumanni</i>	Lesser Kestrel		1		1, 2
	<i>Falco ardosiaceus</i>	Grey Kestrel		1		1, 2
	<i>Polihierax semitorquatus</i>	Pygmy Falco		1		1, 2
	<i>Falco subbuteo</i>	European Hobby		1		1, 2
	<i>Falco concolor</i>	Sooty Falcon		1		1, 2
	<i>Falco amurensis</i>	Eastern Red-footed Falcon		1		1, 2
	<i>Falco vespertinus</i>	Western Red-footed Falcon		1		1, 2
	<i>Falco chicquera</i>	Red-necked Falcon		1		1, 2
	<i>Falco biarmicus</i>	Lanner Falcon		1		1, 2
	<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	Peregrine Falcon		1		1, 2
Galliformes						
Numididae	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	Helmeted Guineafowl	1			1, 2
Phasianidae	<i>Francolinus squamatus</i>	Scaly Francolin		1		1, 2
	<i>Francolinus (Pternistis) nobilis</i>	Handsome francolin		1		1, 2
	<i>Francolinus levaillantii</i>	Red-winged Francolin	1			1, 2
	<i>Francolinus streptophorus</i>	Ring-necked francolin		1		1, 2
	<i>Francolinus coqui</i>	Coqui Francolin	1			1, 2
	<i>Francolinus hildebrandti</i>	Hildebrandt's Francolin		1		1, 2
	<i>Francolinus afer</i>	Red-necked Spurfowl	1		1	1, 2
	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>	Common Quail		1		1, 2
Gruiformes						
Rallidae	<i>Sarothrura pulchra</i>	White-spotted Fluftail		1		1, 2
	<i>Sarothrura rufa</i>	Red-chested Fluftail		1		1, 2
	<i>Sarothrura boehmi</i>	Streaky-breasted Fluftail		1		1, 2
	<i>Crecopsis egregia</i>	African Crake	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Crex crex</i>	Common Crake	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Porzana porzana</i>	Spotted Crake	1			1, 2
	<i>Porzana pusilla</i>	Baillon's Crake		1		1, 2
	<i>Amauromis flavirostris</i>	Black Crake	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Porphyrio porphyrio</i>	Purple Swamphen	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Porphyrio alleni</i>	Lesser Gallinule	1			1, 2
	<i>Rallus caerulescens</i>	African Water Rail	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Fulica cristata</i>	Red-knobbed Coot		1		1, 2
	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	Moorphen	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Gallinula angulata</i>	Lesser Moorphen	1	1	1	1, 2
Gruidae	<i>Balearica regulorum</i>	Grey Crowned Crane		1		1, 2
	<i>Bugeranus carunculatus</i>	Wattled Crane		1		1, 2
Otididae	<i>Neotis denhami</i>	Denham's Bustard	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Eupodotis melanogaster</i>	Black-bellied Bustard	1			2, 3
Charadriiformes						
Jacaniidae	<i>Actophilornis africanus</i>	African Jacana	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Microparra capensis</i>	Lesser Jacana		1		1, 2
Recurvirostridae	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>	Black-winged Stilt	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Recurvirostra avosetta</i>	Avocet	1	1	1	1, 2
Dromatidae	<i>Dromas ardeola</i>	Crab Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
Rostratulidae	<i>Rostratula benghalensis</i>	Painted Snipe	1	1	1	1, 2
Burhinidae	<i>Burhinus capensis</i>	Spotted Dikkop	1			1, 2
	<i>Burhinus vermiculatus</i>	Water Dikkop	1	1	1	1, 2

Order/ Family	Species Name	English Name	RCD	RBD	RCD	Nb
					RBD	Refer.
Glareolidae	<i>Cursorius temminckii</i>	Temminck's Courser		1		1, 2
	<i>Glareola pratincola</i>	Common Pratincole	1		1	1, 2
	<i>Glareola nordmanni</i>	Black-winged Pratincole	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Glareola nuchalis</i>	Rock Pratincole		1		1, 2
	<i>Glareola cinerea</i>	Grey Pratincole		1		1, 2
Charadriidae	<i>Charadrius pecuarius</i>	Kittlitz's Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Charadrius marginatus</i>	White-fronted Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Charadrius tricollaris</i>	Three-banded Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Charadrius forbesi</i>	Forbes's Plover	1			1, 2
	<i>Charadrius hiaticula</i>	Ringed Plover	1	1		1, 2
	<i>Charadrius dubius</i>	Little Ringed Plover	1			1, 2
	<i>Charadrius alexandrinus</i>	Kentish Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Charadrius mongolus</i>	Mongolian Plover		1		1, 2
	<i>Charadrius leschenaultii</i>	Sand Plover		1		1, 2
	<i>Charadrius asiaticus</i>	Caspian Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Vanellus spinosus</i>	Spur-winged Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Vanellus crassirostris</i>	Long-toed Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Vanellus senegallus</i>	Wattled Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Vanellus coronatus</i>	Crowned Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Vanellus lugubris</i>	Lesser Black-winged Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Vanellus superciliosus</i>	Brown-chested Lapwing		1		1, 2
	<i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>	Grey Plover	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Pluvialis fulva</i>	Pacific Golden Plover	1			1, 2
	<i>Philomachus pugnax</i>	Ruff	1	1	1	1, 2
Scolopacidae	<i>Tryngites subrificollis</i>	Buff-breasted Sandpiper	1			1, 2
	<i>Phalaropus lobatus</i>	Red-necked Phalarope		1		1, 2
	<i>Phalaropus fulicarius</i>	Grey Phalarope		1		1, 2
	<i>Actitis (Tringa) hypoleucos</i>	Common Sandpiper	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Tringa glareola</i>	Wood Sandpiper	1			1, 2
	<i>Tringa ochropus</i>	Green Sandpiper		1		1, 2
	<i>Xenus (Tringa) cinereus</i>	Terek Sandpiper	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Tringa nebularia</i>	Common Greenshank	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Tringa stagnatilis</i>	Marsh Sandpiper	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Tringa erythropus</i>	Spotted Redshank	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Tringa totanus</i>	Redshank	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Calidris minuta</i>	Little Stint	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Calidris temminckii</i>	Temminck's Stint	1			1, 2
	<i>Calidris ferruginea</i>	Curlew Sandpiper	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Calidris alpina</i>	Dunlin	1			1, 2
	<i>Limosa limosa</i>	Black-tailed Godwit	1			1, 2
	<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>	Whimbrel	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Numenius arquata</i>	Curlew	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Gallinago gallinago</i>	Common Snipe		1		1, 2
	<i>Gallinago nigripennis</i>	Ethiopian Snipe	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Gallinago media</i>	Great Snipe	1	1	1	1, 2
Stercorariidae	<i>Stercorarius parasiticus</i>	Arctic Skua		1		1, 2
	<i>Stercorarius pomarinus</i>	Pomarine Skua		1		1, 2
Laridae	<i>Larus cirrocephalus</i>	Grey-headed Gull		1		1, 2

Order/ Family	Species Name	English Name	RCD	RBD	RCD RBD	Nb Refer.
	<i>Larus ridibundus</i>	Black-headed Gull	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	Lesser Black-backed Gull		1		1, 2
	<i>Larus ichthyaetus</i>	Great Black-headed Gull		1		1, 2
Sternidae	<i>Sterna bengalensis</i>	Lesser Crested Stern		1		1, 2
	<i>Sterna caspia</i>	Caspian Tern		1		1, 2
	<i>Sterna nilotica</i>	Gull-billed Tern		1		1, 2
	<i>Sterna Hirundo</i>	Common Tern	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Sternula albifrons</i>	Little Tern	1			1, 2
	<i>Chlidonias leucopterus</i>	White-winged Tern	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Chlidonias hybridus</i>	Whiskered Tern	1	1	1	1, 2
Rynchopidae	<i>Rynchops flavirostris</i>	African Skimmer	1	1	1	1, 2
Columbiformes						
Columbidae	<i>Treron calva</i>	African Green-pigeon	1			1, 2
	<i>Columba guinea</i>	Speckled pigeon	1			1, 2
	<i>Columba uncinata</i>	Afep Pigeon		1		1, 2
	<i>Turtur chalcospilos</i>	Emerald-spotted Wood Dove		1		1, 2
	<i>Turtur afer</i>	Blue-spotted Wood- Dove	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Turtur tympanistris</i>	Tembourine Dove	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Oena capensis</i>	Namaqua Dove		1		1, 2
	<i>Streptopelia capicola</i>	Cape Turtle Dove	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Streptopelia semitorquata</i>	Red-eyed Dove	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Streptopelia senegalensis</i>	Laughing Dove	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Streptopelia lugens</i>	Pink-breasted Turtle Dove	1			1, 2
	<i>Columba (Aplopelia) larvata</i>	Lemon Dove		1		1, 2
Psittaciformes						
Psittacidae	<i>Poicephalus suahelicus</i>	Brown-necked Parrot		1		1, 2
Cuculiformes						
Musophagidae	<i>Musophaga rossae</i>	Ross's (Lady) Turaco		1		1, 2
	<i>Corythaixoides leucogaster</i>	White-bellied Go-away Bird		1		1, 2
Cuculidae	<i>Clamator glandarius</i>	Great Spotted Cuckoo		1		1, 2
	<i>Oxylophus (Clamator) levillant</i>	Levaillant's Cuckoo	1			1, 2
	<i>Oxylophus (Clamator) jacobinus</i>	Jacobin Cuckoo	1			1, 2
	<i>Cuculus rochii</i>	Madagascar Lesser Cuckoo		1		1, 2
	<i>Chrysococcyx klaas</i>	Klaas's Cuckoo	1			1, 2
	<i>Chrysococcyx cupreus</i>	Emerald Cuckoo		1		1, 2
	<i>Centropus superciliosus</i>	White-browed Coucal	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Centropus monachus</i>	Blue-headed Coucal	1			1, 2
	<i>Centropus senegalensis</i>	Senegal Coucal	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Centropus cupreicaudus</i>	Coppery-tailed Coucal	1			1, 2
	<i>Centropus grillii</i>	Black Coucal	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Centropus anselli</i>	Gabon Coucal	1			1, 2
	<i>Centropus leucogaster</i>	Black-throated Coucal	1			1, 2
Strigiformes						
Strigidae	<i>Strix woodfordii</i>	Wood Owl	1			1, 2
	<i>Asio capensis</i>	Marsh Owl	1			1, 2
	<i>Otus leucotis</i>	White-faced Scops-owl	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Otus senegalensis</i>	African Scops-owl		1		1, 2
	<i>Bubo lacteus</i>	Verreaux's Eagle-Owl	1			1, 2

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	<i>Bubo africanus</i>	Spotted Eagle-Owl	1			1, 2
Caprimulgiformes						
Caprimulgidae	<i>Caprimulgus fossii</i>	Square-tailed Nightjar	1			1, 2
	<i>Caprimulgus ruwenzorii</i>	Ruwenzori Nightjar		1		1, 2
	<i>Caprimulgus pectoralis</i>	Fiery-necked Nightjar	1			1, 2
	<i>Caprimulgus inornatus</i>	Plain Nighthjar		1		1, 2
Apodiformes						
Apodidae	<i>Apus affinis</i>	Little Swift	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Apus caffer</i>	African White-rumped Swift	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Apus horus</i>	Horus Swift		1		1, 2
	<i>Apus (Tachymarpis) melba</i>	Alpine Swift		1		1, 2
	<i>Apus barbatus</i>	African Black Swift	1			1, 2
	<i>Apus apus</i>	European Swift	1			1, 2
	<i>Cypsiurus parvus</i>	African Palm-Swift	1	1	1	1, 2
Coliidae	<i>Colius striatus</i>	Speckled Mousebird	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Colius leucocephalus</i>	White-headed Mousebird		1		1, 2
	<i>Urocolius (Colius) macrourus</i>	Blue-naped Mousebird		1		1, 2
Trogonidae	<i>Apaloderma vittatum</i>	Bar-tailed Trogon		1		1, 2
Coraciiformes						
Alcedinidae	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	Pied Kingfisher	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Halcyon chelicuti</i>	Striped Kingfisher		1		1, 2
	<i>Halcyon leucocephala</i>	Grey-headed Kingfisher		1		1, 2
	<i>Halcyon albiventris</i>	Brown-hooded Kingfisher	1			1, 2
	<i>Megaceryle maxima</i>	Giant Kingfisher	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Halcyon senegalensis</i>	Woodland Kingfisher	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Alcedo cristata</i>	Malachite Kingfisher	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ispidina (Ceyx) picta</i>	African Pygmy Kingfisher	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Alcedo quadribrachys</i>	Shining-bue Kingfisher	1			1, 2
Meropidae	<i>Merops pusillus</i>	Blue-cheeked Bee-eater	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Merops oreobates</i>	Cinnamon-breasted Bee-eater		1		1, 2
	<i>Merops variegatus</i>	White-cheeked Bee-eater	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Merops albicollis</i>	White-throated Bee-eater	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Merops apiaster</i>	European Bee-eater	1			1, 2
	<i>Merops persicus</i>	Blue-cheeked Bee-eater	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Merops supeciliosus</i>	Madagascar Bee-eater	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Merops bullockoides</i>	White-fronted Bee-eater		1		1, 2
	<i>Merops nubicus</i>	Northern Carmine Bee-eater	1	1	1	1, 2
Coraciidae	<i>Eurystomus glaucurus</i>	Broad-billed Roller	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Coracias caudata</i>	Lilac-breasted Roller		1		1, 2
	<i>Coracias garrulus</i>	European Roller		1		1, 2
Phoeniculidae	<i>Phoeniculus purpureus</i>	Red-billed Wood Hoopoe	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Rhinopomastus cyannomelas</i>	Scimitarbill	1	1	1	1, 2
Upupidae	<i>Upupa africana</i>	African Hoopoe		1		1, 2
	<i>Upupa epops</i>	Eurasian Hoopoe		1		1, 2
Lybiidae	<i>Lybius minor</i>	White-faced Barbet		1		1, 2
	<i>Lybius rubrifacies</i>	Red-faced Barbet		1		1, 2
Piciformes						
Indicatoridae	<i>Indicator indicator</i>	Greater Honeyguide	1	1	1	1, 2

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					RBD	Refer.
	<i>Indicator variegatus</i>	Scaly-throated Honeyguide	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Indicator minor</i>	Lesser Honeyguide		1		1, 2
	<i>Indicator pumilio</i>	Dwarf Honeyguide		1		2, 3
Picidae	<i>Campethera tullbergi</i>	Tullberg's Woodpecker		1		2, 3
	<i>Campethera abingoni</i>	Golden-tailed Woodpecker		1		2, 3
	<i>Campethera cailliautii</i>	Little Spotted Woodpecker		1		2, 3
Eurylaimidae	<i>Pseudocalyptomena graueri</i>	Grauer's Broadbill	1	1	1	1, 2
Pittidae	<i>Pitta angolensis</i>	African pitta		1		2, 3
Passeriformes						
Alaudidae	<i>Mirafra africana</i>	Rufous-naped Lark	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Calandrella cinerea</i>	Red-capped Lark		1		2, 3
	<i>Eremoptrix leucopareia</i>	Fisher's Sparrow-Lark	1			1, 2
	<i>Eremophila alpestris</i>	Horned Lark		1		2, 3
Hirundinidae	<i>Hirundo fuligula</i>	Rock Martin	1			1, 2
	<i>Riparia riparia</i>	Sand Martin	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Riparia cincta</i>	Banded Martin		1		1, 2
	<i>Delichon urbica</i>	Northern House Martin	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Hirundo daurica</i>	Red-rumped Swallow	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Hirundo (Cecropis) abyssinica</i>	Lesser Striped Swallow		1		1, 2
	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Barn Swallow	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Hirundo angolensis</i>	Angola Swallow	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Hirundo aethiopica</i>	Ethiopian Swallow	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Hirundo smithii</i>	White-tailed Swallow	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Psalidoprocne albiceps</i>	White-headed Sawwing	1			1, 2
Motacillidae	<i>Motacilla aguimp</i>	African Pied Wagtail	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Motacilla capensis</i>	Cape Wagtail	1			1, 2
	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	Grey Wagtail	1			1, 2
	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	Yellow Wagtail	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Macronyx croceus</i>	Yellow-throated Longclaw	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Anthus cinnamomeus</i>	African Pipit	1			1, 2
	<i>Anthus leucophrys</i>	Plain-backed Pipit	1			1, 2
	<i>Anthus richardi</i>	Richard's Pipit		1		1, 2
Campephagidae	<i>Campephaga flava</i>	Black Cuckooshrike		1		1, 2
	<i>Coracina (Cebilepyris) caesius</i>	Grey Cuckooshrike		1		1, 2
Pycnonotidae	<i>Nicator chloris</i>	Western Nicator		1		1, 2
	<i>Pycnonotus barbatus</i>	Common Bulbul	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Andropadus latirostris</i>	Yellow-Whiskered Greenbul	1			1, 2
	<i>Chlorocichla flavicollis</i>	Yellow-throated Leaflove	1			1, 2
	<i>Andropadus nigriceps</i>	Mountain Greenbul		1		1, 2
	<i>Andropadus masukuensis</i>	Shelley's Greenbul		1		1, 2
Turdidae	<i>Sheppardia sharpei</i>	Sharpe's Akalat	1			1, 2
	<i>Sheppardia bocagei</i>	Bocage's Akalat	1			1, 2
	<i>Cossypha heuglini</i>	White-browed Robin-chat	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	Rüppell's Robin-Chat		1		1, 2
	<i>Cossypha cyanocampter</i>	Blue-shouldered Robin-Chat		1		1, 2
	<i>Cossypha natalensis</i>	Red-capped Robin-Chat	1			1, 2
	<i>Myrmecocichla nigra</i>	Sooty Chat	1			1, 2
	<i>Cercotrichas quadrivirgata</i>	Eastern Bearded Scrub Robin		1		1, 2

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	<i>Cichladusa arquata</i>	Collared Palm Thrush	1			1, 2
	<i>Zoothera (Geokichla) piaggiae</i>	Abyssinian Ground Thrush	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Zoothera tanganyicae</i>	Kivu Ground Thrush		1		1, 2
	<i>Monticola angolensis</i>	Miombo Rock-Thrush	1	1	1	1, 2
Acrocephalidae	<i>Acrocephalus gracilirostris</i>	Lesser Swamp Warbler	1			1, 2
	<i>Acrocephalus rufescens</i>	Greater Swmp Warbler	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Acrocephalus baeticatus</i>	African Reed Warbler	1			1, 2
	<i>Acrocephalus scirpaceus</i>	Reed Warbler	1			1, 2
	<i>Acrocephalus arundinaceus</i>	Great Reed Warbler	1			1, 2
	<i>Acrocephalus shoenoaenus</i>	Sedge Warbler	1			1, 2
	<i>Chloropeta similis</i>	Mountain yellow warbler	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Hippolais icterina</i>	Icterine Warbler		1		1, 2
Locustellidae	<i>Bradypterus cinnamomeus</i>	Cinnamon Bracken Warbler		1		1, 2
	<i>Bradypterus baboecala</i>	African Bush Warbler	1			1, 2
Sylviidae	<i>Sylvia borin</i>	Garden Warbler	1			1, 2
	<i>Sylvia communis</i>	Common Whitethroat	1			1, 2
	<i>Graueria vittata</i>	Grauer's Warbler	1	1	1	1, 2
Scotocercidae	<i>Hemitesia neumanni</i>	Short-tailed Warbler	1			1, 2
Phylloscopidae	<i>Phylloscopus trochilus</i>	Willow Warbler		1		1, 2
	<i>Phylloscopus laetus</i>	Red-faced Woodland-Warbler		1		1, 2
	<i>Melocichla mentalis</i>	African Mostached Warbler		1		1, 2
Macrosphenidae	<i>Sylvietta leucophrys</i>	White-browed Crombec		1		1, 2
Hylotiidae	<i>Hyliota flavigaster</i>	Yellow-bellied hyliota		1		1, 2
Cisticolidae	<i>Cisticola brunnescens</i>	Pectoral-patch Cisticola		1		1, 2
	<i>Cisticola juncidis</i>	Zitting Cisticola	1			1, 2
	<i>Cisticola ayresii</i>	Wing-snapping Cisticola	1			1, 2
	<i>Cisticola nanus</i>	Tiny Cisticola		1		1, 2
	<i>Cisticola natalensis</i>	Croaking Cisticola	1			1, 2
	<i>Cisticola chiniana</i>	Rattling Cisticola		1		1, 2
	<i>Cisticola galactotes</i>	Winding Cisticola	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Cisticola carruthersi</i>	Carruthers's Cisticola		1		1, 2
	<i>Cisticola pipiens</i>	Chirping Cisticola		1		1, 2
	<i>Cisticola cantans</i>	Singing Cisticola		1		1, 2
	<i>Cisticola erythrops</i>	Red-faced Cisticola	1			1, 2
	<i>Cisticola chubbi</i>	Chubb's Cisticola		1		1, 2
	<i>Prinia subflava</i>	Tawny-flanked Prinia	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Prinia bairdii</i>	Banded Prinia	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Camaroptera brachyura</i>	Bleating Bush Warbler	1			1, 2
	<i>Calamonastes simplex</i>	Grey Wren Warbler		1		1, 2
	<i>Apalis flavida</i>	Yellow-breasted Apalis	1			1, 2
	<i>Apalis (Urorhipis) rufifrons</i>	Red-fronted Warbler	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Apalis argentea</i>	Kungwe Apalis		1		1, 2
	<i>Apalis porphyrolaema</i>	Chestnut-throated Apalis		1		1, 2
	<i>Apalis (Oreolais) ruwenzorii</i>	Rwenzori apalis		1		1, 2
	<i>Apalis personata</i>	Black-faced Apalis		1		2, 3
	<i>Eminia lepida</i>	Grey-capped Warbler	1			1, 2
Muscicapidae	<i>Melaenornis fischeri</i>	White-eyed Slaty-flycatcher		1		1, 3
	<i>Muscicapa adusta</i>	Dusky Flycatcher	1			2, 3

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	<i>Muscicapa cassini</i>	Cassin's Grey Flycatcher	1			2, 3
	<i>Sheppardia aequatorialis</i>	Equatorial Akalat		1		1, 2
	<i>Muscicapa aquatica</i>	Swamp Flycatcher	1			1, 2
	<i>Chamaetylas poliophrys</i>	Red-throated Alethe	1	1	1	1, 3
	<i>Cossyphicula roberti</i>	White-bellied Robin-chat	1	1		1, 3
	<i>Myrmecocichla cinnamomeiventris</i>	Mocking Cliff Chat		1		1, 2
	<i>Myrmecocichla arnoti</i>	Arnot's Chat		1		1, 2
	<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i>	Northern Wheatear		1		1, 2
	<i>Muscicapa boehmi</i>	Böhm's Flycatcher		1		2, 3
	<i>Muscicapa lendu</i>	Chapin's Flycatcher		1		2, 3
	<i>Melaenornis ardesiacus</i>	Yellow-eyed Black-Flycatcher		1		1, 2
Platysteiridae	<i>Batis diops</i>	Ruwenzori Batis		1		1, 2
Monarchidae	<i>Terpsiphone viridis</i>	African Paradise-flycatcher	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Terpsiphone rufiventer</i>	Red-billed Paradise-flycatcher	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Trochocercus albiventris</i>	White-bellied Crested Flycatcher		1		1, 2
Pellorneidae	<i>Illadopsis pyrrhoptera</i>	Rufous-winged Illadopsis		1		1, 2
	<i>Kakamega poliothorax</i>	Grey-chested Babbler		1		1, 2
Leiothrichidae	<i>Pseudoalcippe abyssinica</i>	Ruwenzori Hill Babbler		1		1, 2
	<i>Turdoides sharpei</i>	Sharpe's Pied-Babbler		1		1, 2
	<i>Kupeornis rufocinctus</i>	Red-collared Mountain-Babbler		1		1, 2
	<i>Turdoides hartlaubii</i>	Hartlaub's babbler		1		1, 2
Paridae	<i>Melaniparus fasciiventer</i>	Stripe-breasted Tit		1		2, 3
Timaliidae	<i>Turdoides jardineii</i>	Arrow-marked Babbler		1		1, 2
	<i>Turdoides melanops</i>	Black-faced Babbler		1		1, 2
Zosteropidae	<i>Zosterops senegalensis</i>	Yellow White-ey	1			1, 2
Nectarinidae	<i>Nectarinia kilimensis</i>	Bronze Sunbird	1			1, 2
	<i>Nectarinia purpureiventris</i>	Purple-breasted Sunbird		1		1, 2
	<i>Nectarinia tacazze</i>	Tacazze Sunbird		1		1, 2
	<i>Nectarinia johnstoni</i>	Scarlet-tufted Malachite Sunbird		1		1, 2
	<i>Cyanomitra alinae</i>	Blue-headed Sunbird	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Cinnyris preussi</i>	Northern Double-collared Sunbird		1		1, 2
	<i>Cinnyris regia</i>	Regal Sunbird		1		2, 3
	<i>Cinnyris erythrocerus</i>	Red-chested Sunbird		1		1, 2
	<i>Cinnyris (Nectarinia) cuprea</i>	Copper Sunbird	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Cinnyris (Nectarinia) mariquensis</i>	Marico Sunbird	1			1, 2
	<i>Cinnyris bifasciata</i>	Purple-banded Sunbird	1			1, 2
	<i>Chalcomitra senegalensis</i>	Scarlet-chested Sunbird	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Chalcomitra (Nectarinia) hunteri</i>	Hunter's Sunbird		1		1, 2
	<i>Cinnyris erythrocerca</i>	Red-chested Sunbird	1	1	1	1, 2
Oriolidae	<i>Oriolus percivali</i>	Mountain Oriole		1		1, 2
	<i>Oriolus oratus</i>	African Golden Oriole		1		1, 2
	<i>Oriolus oriolus</i>	Eurasian Golden Oriole		1		1, 2
Laniidae	<i>Lanius collaris</i>	Common Fiscal	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Lanius dorsalis</i>	Taita Fiscal	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Lanius cabanisi</i>	Long-tailed Fiscal	1			1, 2
	<i>Lanius excubitoroides</i>	Grey-backed Fiscal	1			1, 2
	<i>Lanius minor</i>	Lesser Grey Shrike	1			1, 2
	<i>Lanius collurio</i>	Red-backed Shrike		1		1, 2
	<i>Corvinella corvina</i>	Yellow-billed Shrike		1		1, 2

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Malaconotidae	<i>Laniarius poensis</i>	Mountain Sooty Boubou		1		1, 2
	<i>Laniarius erythrogaster</i>	Black-headed Gonolek	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Laniarius ferrugineus</i>	Southern Boubou	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Tchagra senegala</i>	Black-crowned Tchagra	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Tchagra australis</i>	Brown-crowned Tchagra		1		1, 2
	<i>Telophorus dohertyi</i>	Doherty's Bush-shrike	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Malachonotus blanchoti</i>	Grey-headed Bush-shrike		1		1, 2
Vangidae	<i>Megabias flammulatus</i>	African Shrike-flycatcher	1	1	1	1, 3
Dicruridae	<i>Dicrurus adsimilis</i>	Fork-tailed Drongo	1			1, 2
Corvidae	<i>Corvus albus</i>	Pied Crow	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Corvus albicollis</i>	White-necked Raven	1	1	1	1, 2
Sturnidae	<i>Poeoptera stuhlmanni</i>	Stuhlmann's Starling	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Onychognathus morio</i>	Red-winged Starling		1		1, 2
	<i>Onychognathus walleri</i>	Waller's Starling		1		1, 2
	<i>Onychognathus tenuirostris</i>	Slender-billed Starling		1		1, 2
	<i>Buphagus africanus</i>	Yellow-billed Oxpecker		1		1, 2
	<i>Lamprotornis purpureus</i>	Purple Starling	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Lamprotornis splendidus</i>	Splendid Starling		1		1, 2
	<i>Cinnyricinclus leucogaster</i>	Violet-backed Starling	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Cinnyricinclus (Poeoptera) sharpii</i>	Sharpe's starling		1		1, 2
Passeridae	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House Sparrow	1			1, 2
	<i>Passer griseus</i>	Common Grey-headed Sparrow	1	1	1	1, 2
Ploceidae	<i>Ploceus cucullatus</i>	Black-headed Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ploceus intermedius</i>	Lesser Masked Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ploceus taeniopterus</i>	Northern Masked Weaver	1			1, 2
	<i>Ploceus reichardi</i>	Tanzania Masked Weaver	1			1, 2
	<i>Ploceus ocularis</i>	Spectacled Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ploceus spekei</i>	Speke's Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ploceus baglafecht</i>	Baglafecht Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Amblyospiza albifrons</i>	Tchick-billed Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ploceus luteolus</i>	Little Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ploceus pelzelni</i>	Slender-billed Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ploceus melanocephalus</i>	Black-headed Weaver		1		1, 2
	<i>Ploceus castanops</i>	Northern Brown-throated Weaver		1		1, 2
	<i>Ploceus superciliosus</i>	Compact Weaver	1			1, 2
	<i>Ploceus xanthops</i>	Large Golden Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ploceus alienus</i>	Strange Weaver	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Ploceus melanogaster</i>	Black-billed Weaver		1		1, 2
	<i>Ploceus insignis</i>	Brown-capped Weaver		1		1, 2
	<i>Quelea quelea</i>	Red-billed Quelea	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Quelea cardinalis</i>	Cardinal Quelea	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Euplectes axillaris</i>	Red-shouldered Widowbird	1			1, 2
	<i>Euplectes capensis</i>	Yellow Bishop	1			1, 2
	<i>Euplectes macrourous</i>	Yellow-wanted Widowbird	1			1, 2
	<i>Euplectes afer</i>	Yellow-crowned Bishop	1			1, 2
	<i>Euplectes albonotatus</i>	White-winged Widowbird	1			1, 2
	<i>Euplectes orix</i>	Red Bishop	1	1	1	1, 2

Order/ Family	Species Name	English Name	RCD	RBD	RCD RBD	Nb Refer.
	<i>Euplectes nigroventris</i>	Zanzibar Red Bishop	1			1, 2
	<i>Euplectes franciscanus</i>	Northern Red Bishop	1			1, 2
	<i>Euplectes hordeaceus</i>	Black-winged Red Bishop	1			1, 2
Estrildidae	<i>Lagonosticta senegala</i>	Red-billed Firefinch	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Lagonosticta rubricata</i>	Blue-billed Firefinch	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Pytilia afra</i>	Orange-winged Pytilia	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Nesocharis ansorgei</i>	White-collared Oliveback		1		1, 2
	<i>Pytilia melba</i>	Melba Finch		1		1, 2
	<i>Euschistospiza cinereovinacea</i>	Dusky Twinspot	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Cryptospiza salvadorii</i>	Abyssinian Crimson-wing		1		1, 2
	<i>Cryptospiza reichenovii</i>	Red Crimson-wing		1		1, 2
	<i>Cryptospiza jacksoni</i>	Dusky Crimsonwing		1		1, 2
	<i>Hypargos niveoguttatus</i>	Peter's Twinspot	1			1, 2
	<i>Uraeginthus bengalus</i>	Red-cheeked Cordon-bleu		1		1, 2
	<i>Estrilda melanotis</i>	Yellow-bellied Waxbill		1		2, 3
	<i>Estrilda astrild</i>	Common Waxbill	1			1, 2
	<i>Estrilda rhodopyga</i>	Crimson-rumped Waxbill	1			1, 2
	<i>Estrilda nonnula</i>	Black-crowned Waxbill	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Estrida charmaosyna</i>	Black-cheeked Waxbill		1		1, 2
	<i>Amandava subflava</i>	Zebra Waxbill	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Lonchura cucullata</i>	Bronze Mannikin	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Lonchura (nigriceps) bicolor</i>	Red-backed Mannikin	1	1	1	1, 2
Viduidae	<i>Vidua macroura</i>	Pin-tailed Whydah	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Vidua chalybeata</i>	Village Indigobird	1	1	1	1, 2
Fringillidae	<i>Crithagra burtoni</i>	Thick-billed Seedeater		1		1, 2
	<i>Crithagra striolatus</i>	Streaky Seedeater	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Serinus frontalis</i>	Western Citril		1		1, 2
	<i>Serinus sulphuratus</i>	Bully Canary	1			1, 2
	<i>Serinus mozambicus</i>	Yellow-fronted Canary	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Serinus citrinelloides</i>	African Citrill	1			1, 2
	<i>Serinus leucopygius</i>	White-rumped Serin	1	1	1	1, 2
	<i>Serinus striolatus</i>	Streaky Seedeater	1	1	1	1, 2
18 Orders/ 84 Families	490 Species		301	387	197	
	Percentages		34	44	22	

Source: Our fieldwork of 2019-2021 and the following references: (1) (Stevenson & Fanshawe, 2002); (2) (Fishpool & Evans, 2001); (3) (Williams & Arlott, 1988).

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